

DEVELOPMENT OF A STATIONARY PARTIAL DISCHARGE MONITORING SYSTEM
FOR HIGH-VOLTAGE ROTATING MACHINE STATOR WINDINGS

Richard C. Arbour

Bert Milano

Bureau of Reclamation
Denver Office, PO Box 25007
Denver Federal Center, Denver CO 80225

Abstract - The stationary partial discharge detector developed by the Bureau of Reclamation provides an economical method of monitoring partial discharge activity in high-voltage motor/generator stator windings. No physical connection to the stator coil or winding is required for this monitoring system; therefore, the integrity of the winding insulation is not compromised. The system can be used to monitor partial discharge during normal on-line operation so that readings reflect actual steady-state running conditions of the winding. Rising levels of partial discharge activity can provide an early warning of insulation deterioration, permitting repairs before serious damage or an inservice failure occurs.

Introduction

Partial discharge activity in a stator winding is a significant indicator of insulation quality and can be used to determine the relative integrity of the insulation system. A discharge of electric current occurs when the dielectric breakdown voltage of a gas trapped in a void surrounded by an insulating material is exceeded, causing the gas to ionize. The ionization, or breakdown, is equivalent to the application of a voltage step across the void capacitance. The charge transferred in this process is a measure of the magnitude and intensity of the partial discharge. These discharge currents can occur within an insulation system if gas-filled voids are present within the insulation material, in the boundary between the copper coil and insulation, or between the insulation and the stator iron. Discharges between the insulation and the stator iron can occur if the conductive shielding system is damaged or if there is a loose bar floating in the slot. This microsparking, in its most serious form, is referred to as "slot discharge" and can destroy a stator winding within a month. The sparking or ionization process releases a burst of high-frequency RF (radio frequency) energy which can be detected a short distance from the source. In most instances, a discharge occurs each time the a-c electric field impressed across the void or gap rises to the voltage breakdown level. In both instances, a somewhat nonrepetitive pulse train-type envelope of RF energy at twice the power system frequency can be generated.

The time-averaged intensity of the RF energy is proportional to the local density and size of ionizing voids and discharge gaps in the winding. Many other factors also affect the radiated energy, but are not addressed in this paper. Measurements of peak and average RF intensity and, more importantly, changes in these levels over time can be used as a qualitative indication in determining the mechanical and electrical condition of the winding. A simple pickup coil device and RF receiver can be used to detect voids and to locate the portion of the winding responsible for the discharges. This paper addresses the use of permanently installed inductive pickup coils to provide long-term on-line monitoring of generator winding partial discharges.

Machine History

Unit G-19 at Grand Coulee Third Powerplant is rated 600 MW, 0.98 power factor, 15 kV L-L, and 72 r/min. The stator winding contains 750 single-turn coils and has an epoxy-mica flake insulation system with a groundwall thickness of 160 mils, which includes 6 mils of 1/2-lap-wrapped polyester binder tape on the outer surface. Each phase consists of 10 parallel circuits with 25 series coils per parallel circuit. Several years after installation, an inspection of the original 13-year-old winding revealed the coils were loose and vibrating radially in the stator slots. The vibration caused extensive damage in a stepladder-like wear pattern to the coil insulation and the conductive shielding paint system. The top insulation layers were damaged at the rear surface of each coil in the bottom of the slot. Side bar damage was restricted mainly to the conductive shielding paint system and was judged to be only superficial because the side insulation was not damaged.

Permanent repairs included replacing coils having significant insulation damage and rewedging the entire winding. Coils having only minor damage to the conductive paint shielding system were repaired in place with applications of conductive paint injected through the stator iron air passage cooling ducts. This repair method proved to be inadequate when, for unrelated reasons, several of these recoated coils were later removed from the stator. The additional conductive paint had reestablished only about 25 percent of the damaged conductive shield. It is possible that the wedge removal, the cleaning, and the rewedging operations also contributed to further deterioration of the conductive shielding and semi-conductive grading paint systems. A problem inherent with this particular insulation system is that the coil surface has very poor adhesive qualities. This results in a fragile conductive shielding system that is easily damaged. The conductive paint flakes off very easily. Rewedging and wedge removal operations had obviously destroyed a large area of the conductive coating on the boreside surface of the coil.

In 1982, the rotor was removed to repair the turbine, inspect the windings, and repair the semi-conductive grading paint. It was found that several of the coils had burn rings in the grading paint. A detailed inspection indicated that the coils were still tightly wedged. Partial discharge activity was monitored with a hand-held corona probe similar to the Tennessee Valley Authority design. This enhanced probe is battery powered, portable, and insulated to protect the operator. Measurements were made with an RF pickup coil placed against the slot wedge of the coil to be monitored. The receiver measures peak levels of RF energy at about 5.0 MHz. At this frequency, the radiation attenuates rapidly with distance, thereby permitting the operator to isolate the signal source (partial discharges) to a section of a coil. Measurements with the corona probe revealed 14 slots with relatively high readings and 2 slots with extremely high readings.

Over concern for the high corona probe readings, the grading paint burn rings, and high concentrations of ozone produced during operation, a series of tests were performed to evaluate the condition of the insulation system. The results of a blackout (total darkness) test, ozone concentration test, and visual inspection indicated that extensive low-level electrical discharge activity was occurring in the stator slots. The high corona probe readings in the 16 slots were attributed to both internal and external discharge activity. Internal partial discharges can indirectly cause deterioration of the epoxy binder on the surface of the conductor strands and between the layers of groundwall insulation. Deterioration of the strand binder can loosen the strands and allow them to vibrate in the magnetic field, eventually causing strand-to-strand faults. In extreme cases, the vibrating strands can wear through the layers of groundwall insulation, eventually resulting in phase-to-ground faults.

The external low-level discharge activity can eventually erode the conductive shielding paint so that slot discharge activity will damage the insulation system from the outside.

Course of Action

Little was known about the low-level slot ionization and the potential for damage, or of the processes involved in the 16 coils having high corona probe readings.

Rather than needlessly rewind or make extensive repairs to the winding, Reclamation decided to perform accelerated aging tests on a bar having a damaged conductive shielding system. In addition, an on-line slot discharge monitor, if possible to install, would provide valuable information regarding the condition and discharge mechanism of the 16 coils having high corona probe readings. The major concern was that the off-line corona probe measurements could be misleading if on-line mechanical vibration was a necessary ingredient to the slot discharge equation.

This need for an on-line monitor led to the development of a permanently mounted on-line slot discharge monitor probe.

Performance Requirements for the Stationary Partial Discharge Monitor

Several factors were considered in the design of the stationary partial discharge monitor. The most important was that the generator insulation system remain intact. Direct connection to the generator winding would not be permitted. It was decided that the partial discharge RF energy would be monitored with an isolated inductive pickup coil similar to the detector used on the hand-held corona probe. Each detector had to be permanently mounted in a secure, protected, low-voltage area of the core with coaxial signal leads brought out to terminals at a location accessible to plant operators when the generator was in operation. The detectors had to be compatible with the existing hand-held corona probe meter used to measure the average peak level of partial discharge activity at a frequency of 5.0 MHz.

Description of Stationary Partial Discharge Monitor

The stationary partial discharge monitoring system consists of a permanently mounted induction pickup coil and a detachable RF receiver which measures the peak amplitude of the 5-MHz burst associated with the partial discharge activity. Signal

strength is displayed in dimensionless units for obvious calibration-related reasons. At times, the device has been calibrated in terms of microvolts induced in the ferrite probe antenna. The induction pickup coil is mounted at the bottom of the stator core (see figure). One pickup coil is installed behind the slot of each coil to be monitored. A stainless steel bracket is bolted to the bottom clamping finger support ring with two 1/4-inch bolts and bolt retainers. The bracket supports the induction pickup coil just below the stator iron with 1/8- to 1/4-inch of air space between the stator coil being monitored and the pickup coil. The pickup coil is a ferrite rod wound with five turns of #16 AWG magnet wire. The ferrite rod is a Fair-Rite #61 material which is designed for operation in a frequency spectrum that spans 5 MHz. The insulated ferrite rods with coils are riveted and epoxied to the stainless steel brackets. Each five-turn coil is connected to a 15-foot RG 58 A/U coaxial cable. The receiver end of the coaxial cable is terminated in the generator air housing with a bulkhead-type coaxial connector. These connectors may be conveniently grouped to enhance accessing several monitoring points. A 6-foot length of RG 58 A/U coaxial cable is used to connect the receiver to each separate probe.

Detail of stationary partial discharge monitor installation

Partial Discharge Measurements

The G-19 hand-held corona probe measurements made with the rotor removed required a separate a-c power source to energize the winding. The neutral end of each phase was isolated so that any phase could be energized with the other two grounded. In turn, each ungrounded phase was energized at approximately 90 percent of rated line-to-ground voltage, thereby providing a uniform conductor-to-groundwall voltage

stress on all coils in each parallel string. This exaggerated the partial discharge level of coils that normally operate below the test voltage, but was considered in the evaluation.

Coils having the highest hand-held corona probe readings taken during a test conducted on August 24, 1983, were selected for permanent monitoring. The exploratory hand-held probe measurements were made along the entire length of the slots with the winding energized at 8 kV rms, phase to ground. Very high radio frequency signal strength readings of 250 and 120 were obtained from slots 16 and 108, respectively, after the winding had been energized for 2 hours. The coil in the front of slot 16 is 21st (from neutral) in a string of 25 and is normally energized at 7.3 kV rms. The back half of this coil is in slot 9 where the stationary inductive pickup coil was mounted. The coil in the front of slot 108 is 20th in a string of 25 and is normally energized at 6.9 kV rms. The back half of this coil is in slot 101 where another inductive pickup coil was mounted. The coil in the front of slot 28 (back half in 21) was selected as a control slot since this coil is 20th in a string of 25. This coil had normal corona probe readings (less than 20). An inductive pickup coil was mounted at the bottom of slot 21.

Reclamation experience with this particular corona probe meter has shown that RF signal strength readings from 0 to 50 indicate very minor, if any, discharges and are normally associated with little or no deterioration. Readings between 50 and 100 indicate minor to moderate deterioration, between 100 and 150 indicate moderate to major deterioration, and over 150 indicate very serious discharge activity and associated deterioration. New windings, depending on type and/or manufacturer, typically have readings below 10 to 20. The degree of deterioration for various corona probe readings has been determined from extensive field experience and has been supported by laboratory dissection and analysis of numerous coils removed from Reclamation generators during the past 10 years.

While experimenting with the installation of the permanent probes, it was observed that discharge levels from the two coils having the highest readings increased significantly with time while discharge levels of other coils decreased slightly or stayed about the same over time. After installation of the rotor, readings were taken with the standard hand-held corona probe and the stationary probes at 10 and 50 minutes after initial energization. The machine was at standstill and energized at 7.4 kV line to ground. The readings were as follows:

Stator slot number	Standard probe reading at		Stationary probe reading at	
	bottom of core, top of slot		bottom of core, bottom of slot	
	10 min	50 min	10 min	50 min
9	2	24	1	1
101	4	80	7	19
21(control)	2	8	6	8

The stationary probe readings are lower due to signal attenuation through the winding and through the longer stationary probe signal leads. The 1/8- to 1/4-inch space between the probe and core also contributes to the attenuation.

Results

The measurements at the time the stationary probes were installed established benchmark levels of partial discharge activity. Thereafter, on-line measurements have been compared to these benchmark standstill readings to determine actual running conditions and trends. On-line measurements made in February 1987 and July 1988 at various var and watt loadings have all been substantially lower than the benchmark readings. The range of readings to date is about 7 to 10 and appears to be unrelated to machine loading.

It appears that the readings:

1. Do not increase in the presence of coil vibration during on-line operation
2. Do not change with loading
3. Decrease substantially with time from initial energization
4. Are not increasing over time.

On the basis of this monitoring program, it was decided not to replace the 16 coils. They will continue to be monitored annually.

Summary

The work performed to date, while meeting our needs in this particular situation, barely scratches the surface. Future stationary probe designs should incorporate lower frequency signals to improve sensitivity and reduce attenuation effects. Much could be done in terms of developing digital signal analysis, directional monitoring, and differential measurement techniques similar to those used in the standard PDA (partial discharge analyzer) currently on the market. Perhaps research using inductive noncontact-type probes in conjunction with a PDA should be considered. This would take advantage of the wealth of information, knowledge, and research performed to date involving the PDA and possibly eliminate the cost of the PDA high-voltage couplers, as well as the objections raised by some regarding the attachment of couplers to windings. In instances involving large hydrogenerators that have 10 parallel circuits per phase, complete and adequate coverage of a winding may be feasible and less expensive using inductive pickup coils.